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Multi-level Validation of Direct Sampling Time Domain Measuring Receivers

IVAN STRUZHKO¹, STUDENT MEMBER, IEEE, MARC GARCÍA-BERMÚDEZ^{2,3},
JORDI SOLÉ-LLOVERAS^{2,3}, MEMBER, IEEE, MANUEL AÑÓN-CANCELA⁴,
TOM HARTMAN¹, MEMBER, IEEE, MARCO A. AZPÚRUA^{2,3}, SENIOR MEMBER, IEEE,
FRANK LEFERINK^{1,5}, FELLOW, IEEE

¹Department of EEMCS, University of Twente, 7522 NB Enschede, The Netherlands

²EMC Electromagnetic BCN S.L. (EMC Barcelona), 08034 Barcelona, Spain

³Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, 08034 Barcelona, Spain

⁴Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial Esteban Terradas (INTA), 28850 Madrid, Spain

⁵THALES Nederland B.V., 7554 RR Hengelo, The Netherlands

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: Ivan Struzhko (e-mail: ivan.struzhko@utwente.nl).

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ABSTRACT Although the time domain approach to electromagnetic interference evaluation offers numerous advantages, including shorter test duration and multi-channel acquisition, its practical adoption remains limited. This is mainly because existing standards, such as CISPR 16-1-1, do not explicitly address direct sampling time domain measuring receivers or define specific calibration and validation procedures for them. While several studies have demonstrated successful use cases, a comprehensive validation of such systems has not yet been performed. This paper presents multi-level experimental validations of time domain measuring receivers, focusing on the direct sampling approach and oscilloscope-based implementations. Firstly, meta-comparisons of FFT-based receivers are made using calibration data obtained from certificates of accredited laboratories. Then, controlled signal sources with known time and spectral characteristics are used to cross-check with different measuring receiver models. Finally, several instruments are benchmarked with respect to their standard detector outputs when measuring the emissions of a power converter while spread spectrum techniques are used. The results show good agreement between the measuring receivers in the time domain and the tested conventional receivers in the frequency domain within the standard error, even though the complexity of the measured signals is different.

INDEX TERMS Compliance, electromagnetic emissions, measuring receiver, time-domain, validation

I. INTRODUCTION

TWO approaches are primarily employed regarding the electromagnetic emission measurement instruments according to the standard method [1]. The classical one uses receivers with superheterodyne architecture, which allows for large dynamic range even at high frequencies due to its scalability. On the other hand, FFT-based receivers digitally process the time-domain emission data to obtain accurate spectrum estimates while accelerating the frequency scans and allowing for real-time measurements.

The frequency-swept approach used by superheterodyne receivers is intrinsically slow and unsuited for measuring short-time emission events and time-variant electromagnetic interference (EMI), leading to potential detection errors and underestimating actual disturbance levels. Some real examples of time-varying emissions sources include those arising from different operation modes, such as the acceleration and deceleration of electric motors [2], [3] or spread spectrum (SS) based pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques used in modern switch mode power supplies [4].

The development of time-domain EMI measurement systems has transformed electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) testing, offering faster and more detailed signal analysis compared to conventional frequency-domain approaches. Important milestones in the development of the time-domain EMI measurement approach are indicated in section II below. Among the main advantages of time-domain receivers that have been recognized in recent studies are the following. First, they shorten the test duration by capturing all necessary data over a single operating cycle of the equipment under test (EUT) [5].

Moreover, implementing the time-domain EMI measurements approach can help overcome the challenges of in situ electromagnetic emissions assessments, as shown in [6], [7] and facilitates synchronous multi-channel acquisitions within a single system as demonstrated in [8] for the case of multi-line conducted emissions tests, or in [9] and [10] where multiple antennas are used to measure H-Field and E-Field simultaneously. Furthermore, time-domain receivers enable spectrogram visualizations, aiding in EMI characterization and classification.

The advantages of the time-domain EMI measurement approach are driving its increasing adoption, but still, its integration into compliance testing remains challenging due to the lack of explicit standardization. For example, the CISPR 16-1-1 standard [1] covers FFT-based receivers in a broad manner; however, implementations based on direct sampling instruments are not explicitly mentioned. Also, the said standard only gathers requirements that are common for any measuring receiver architecture under a black box approach. This means there are no specific calibration requirements for time domain EMI receivers, and some controversy remains concerning different measuring receiver architectures providing non-identical measurement results. Furthermore, only limited validation of these systems has been reported, often focusing on individual performance metrics rather than a comprehensive, multi-level assessment.

To bridge this gap, we present a multi-level validation approach that systematically evaluates direct sampling time-domain EMI receivers against industry-standard frequency-domain EMI receivers. Unlike previous studies, this paper introduces a comprehensive validation strategy that includes follow stages: establishing a meta-analysis of calibration data to verify baseline accuracy, conducting controlled signal experiments to test time-domain EMI receiver performance across different CISPR frequency bands, and benchmarking real-world EMI measurements using complex load cases (e.g., DC/DC converters with spread spectrum techniques). Thus, validation is achieved by comparing FFT-based direct sampling receivers and other measurement receiver architectures in experiments organised at three levels of complexity. In this context, the complexity of the experiment is related to the number of parameters required to define the reference signal. It provides empirical evidence to support the inclusion of direct sampling

EMI receivers in future EMC standardization efforts. In total, this work reports five experiments made by three independent groups and institutions and considers nine different measuring receiver models. By addressing these gaps, this work ensures the reliability of direct sampling EMI receivers and lays the foundation for their broader adoption in compliance testing and EMC research.

The rest of the paper is as follows. Section II presents a background on time-domain EMI measurements. Section III presents a detailed methodology for each experiment. Section IV then presents the results and analyses the adequacy of using direct sampling measurement devices for EMI measurements. Finally, section V discusses the overall result obtained from the research and presents a conclusion.

II. BACKGROUND

The time-domain EMI measurement techniques have evolved as a powerful alternative to traditional frequency-domain receivers, offering faster and more comprehensive analysis of electromagnetic emissions. While superheterodyne receivers have been widely used for compliance testing, their frequency-swept approach is slow and struggles with time-variant signals, making them less effective for modern electronic systems. The foundation for time-domain EMI measurements was laid in [11] and [12], where authors introduced direct sampling and digital processing to extract amplitude and phase information across the entire frequency band, enabling real-time EMI analysis. A milestone was the digital model for the quasi-peak detector presented in [13].

Subsequent research presented in [14] focused on achieving CISPR 16-1-1 compliance, particularly for high-frequency measurements above 1 GHz, demonstrating in [15] that time-domain EMI receivers could replace conventional EMI measurement systems, including the measurement of discontinuous disturbances in [16]. Later enhancements were reported in [17], including modifications to the hardware architecture to achieve lower noise levels, increased measurement bandwidth, and a maximum measurable frequency of up to 40 GHz.

The trend in FFT-based measuring receivers resulted in various commercial instruments capable of real-time performance with increasingly higher measurement bandwidth. Due to their characteristics, these instruments ultimately became high-end solutions. Additionally, the time domain information has remained largely unexploited in such instruments, as EMC standards for emissions tests do not require it for compliance evaluation.

At that point, Azpúrua *et al.* began working on a software layer implementation of the CISPR 16-1-1 measuring receiver, which could be combined with multiple general-purpose sampling instruments. For their practicality and wide availability, oscilloscopes were extensively used as direct measuring instruments, and the acquired signals were processed using the methods described in [18]. The results demonstrated excellent performance and revealed

new potential applications for the statistical analysis of interferences presented in [19] and [20], as well as their decomposition into transient and continuous modes in [21]. Azpúrua et al. called their approach “full time domain emission measurement systems” where the directly sampled waveform information is kept as an integral part of the measurement results and the utilization of time domain data is conducted more broadly.

Advancements in oscilloscope technology and the affordability of direct sampling FFT-based receivers have made time-domain EMI measurements a powerful tool for tackling real-world EMI challenges. Researchers have demonstrated their effectiveness in multi-channel, multi-transducer setups for faster EMI analysis [22], improved detection of low-repetitiveness cyclo-stationary disturbances [23], and precise characterization of impulsive noise affecting energy meters [24]. In aerospace applications, time-domain methods have been used to analyze magnetic field emissions from reaction wheels [2], while their advantages for in situ EMI assessments in harsh environments have been highlighted in recent studies [6].

Assuring the quality and reproducibility of emissions measurement is mandatory in the context of compliance testing. Therefore, the appropriate performance must be guaranteed for direct sampling FFT-based measuring receivers. One way to approach this problem is through a traceable calibration, as with any type of measuring receiver. This is a problem explored in [25], and it is found that typical measuring receiver calibration procedures are non-optimal for direct sampling implementations. In other papers, the measurement accuracy [26], [27] and dynamic performance [28] of full time domain EMI measurement systems are evaluated. However, the lack of a benchmark comparing commercial solutions versus the direct-sampling implementations of FFT-based measuring receivers resulted in an information gap and speculation.

Given the many applications of direct sampling FFT-based measuring receivers explored in academia and research activities, their widespread acceptance and use could benefit from their clear coverage in EMC standards. To support the intended standardization work, on the one hand, the signal processing methods must be thoroughly explained and checked in a wide range of configurable parameters of the spectral estimation functions, as presented in [29] using systematic numerical experiments.

As a next step, this work tackled the empirical part of this endeavor, providing a robust validation scheme that follows a multi-level approach. It introduces a structured validation approach, systematically comparing direct sampling time-domain EMI receivers with commercial CISPR-compliant receivers through a multi-level benchmarking process. By providing empirical evidence supporting the accuracy, reliability, and standardization of time-domain EMI receivers, this work aims to facilitate their broader adoption in compliance testing and EMC research.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the measurement setups, procedures followed, and intended characteristics of the measured signals for each experiment. Experiments are arranged in the order of increasing complexity of the measured signal and identified through a code. The independent teams involved in each experiment are labelled as “A”, “B” and “C” for INTA, EMC Barcelona and the University of Twente, respectively. The summary of each experiment is given in Table 1 while the specific details are given in the following subsections.

TABLE 1. Summary of the experiments.

Code	Experiment description	Team
<i>E0</i>	Meta-analysis of calibration data of EMI receivers using standard reference signals.	A
<i>E1.1</i>	Verifications using controlled modulated signals. Pulse modulated sinewave, CISPR bands B to D.	A+B
<i>E1.2</i>	Verifications using controlled modulated signals. Alternative signals, CISPR band A.	C
<i>E2.1</i>	Realistic emissions measurements using a commercial off-the-shelf (COST) DC/DC buck-boost converter.	A+B
<i>E2.2</i>	Realistic emissions measurements using a DC/DC GaN converter with alternative PWM.	C

This study considers various instruments from different manufacturers and architectures, as depicted in Table 2. To facilitate the presentation of the results, the EMI receivers in the selected sample have an associated identification code (ID). Receivers ID R1 and R2 are those based on direct sampling methods as described in [29]. It must be noted that all experiments use at least three different receivers, and the direct sampling approach is present in all experiments at least through one of the samples.

TABLE 2. List of measuring receivers considered during the experiments.

ID	Measuring receivers	<i>E0</i>	<i>E1.1</i>	<i>E1.2</i>	<i>E2.1</i>	<i>E2.2</i>
R1	emiGO ^(*,Δ) + R&S RTO64 DC - 3 GHz	✓	✓	-	✓	-
R2	emiGO ^(*,Δ) + PS5444D DC - 200 MHz	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
R3	R&S ESI ^(Δ) (20 Hz - 40 GHz)	-	✓	-	-	-
R4	R&S ESW ^(Δ) (1 Hz - 8 GHz)	-	✓	-	✓	-
R5	R&S ESW ^(Δ) (1 Hz - 26.5 GHz)	✓	-	-	-	-
R6	R&S ESW ^(Δ) (1 Hz - 44 GHz)	✓	-	-	-	-
R7	Keysight N9038B MXE ^(Δ) (3 Hz - 44 GHz)	✓	-	-	-	-
R8	R&S ESI ^(Δ) (9 kHz - 7 GHz)	-	-	✓	-	✓
R9	Signal Hound BB60C (9 kHz - 6 GHz)	-	-	✓	-	✓

NOTE: The instruments marked (*) are those based on direct sampling implementations. The symbol (Δ) highlights CISPR 16-1-1 compliance according to specifications, at least in the frequency range of the experiments.

The selected instruments represent a cross-section of measurement equipment commonly used in electromagnetic emissions testing, covering a range of receiver architectures (e.g., direct sampling, superheterodyne), brands, and typical performance classes. The comparison focuses primarily on amplitude-related parameters, such as deviations in measured signal levels and the behavior of standard detectors: peak (PK), quasi-peak (QP), and average (AVE), as defined in CISPR 16-1-1, since these are directly used in emissions compliance assessment. Their implementation in the context of direct sampling receivers is discussed in detail in [29].

A. META-ANALYSIS OF CALIBRATION DATA

This experiment used calibration data extracted from certificates produced by ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratories. For calibration of measuring receivers, reference signals are typically sinewaves and baseband pulses. That means they have low complexity and are easily generated with lower measurement uncertainty in comparison to the signals used in the rest of the experiments. In particular, we focused on the baseline parameters required in [1]. All receivers are considered to comply with CISPR 16-1-1 according to their specifications. Calibration data confirmed this. However, we wanted to check how close direct sampling implementations performed with respect to the high-end receivers in these calibration conditions.

B. PULSE MODULATED SINEWAVE

In this experiment, we measured pulse modulated sinewaves according to the characteristics defined in Table 3. The setup was configured with the output of the signal generator directly connected to the input of the measuring receiver. The source was a vector signal generator model Agilent E4438C (250 kHz - 6 GHz). This signal allows for the verification and comparison of the response of the weighting detectors at a given frequency. Tested frequencies are found in CISPR bands B to D. This experiment follows a full factorial design, with a total of 90 measurements executed using the four distinct receivers considered.

TABLE 3. E1.1 - Signal characteristics.

Parameters	Value
Level (dB μ V):	66
Tested frequency, (MHz):	1, 10, 100, 500
Pulse duration, τ (μ s):	10, 20, 50
Pulse period, T (μ s):	100, 1000

C. ALTERNATIVE GENERATED SIGNALS

For the modulated signals in Table 4, this experiment evaluates the performance of measuring receivers within the CISPR band A. The test signals were chosen to comprise some of the characteristics of the emissions of power converters. Test signals E1.2.(1,2,3) have a constant frequency content while E1.2.(4,5,6) change their frequency content over the measurement time.

TABLE 4. E1.2 - Test signal characteristics.

ID	Test signal	Parameters
E1.2.1	Sinewave	100 kHz, 1 V _{RMS} .
E1.2.2	Multitone	20/40/60/80/100/120/140 kHz, 100 mV _{RMS} each.
E1.2.3	Square pulse	20 kHz, 1 V _{PPK} .
E1.2.4	Chirp pulse	80 kHz - 120 kHz, 1 V _{RMS} , $t_{spr} = 20$ ms.
E1.2.5	Spread spectrum square signal	18 kHz - 22 kHz, 1 V _{PPK} , $t_{spr} = 20$ ms.

The test signals are generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Teledyne T3AFG120. The measurement time is set to 100 ms to ensure an integer number of periods for all test signals. Then the measurement output of R2 and R9 are compared with R8 which is taken as the reference.

D. EMISSIONS OF A COST DC/DC CONVERTER

The conducted emissions of the device reference AZDelivery XL-4016E1 are measured using the setup presented in Figs. 1 and 2. The device input voltage is set to 12 V, the output voltage is adjusted to 5 V and the switching frequency is fixed at approximately 64 kHz. The device is loaded with a resistor (1 Ω - 200 W). The transducer for measuring the disturbance voltage in the positive and negative input lines is a SCHWARZBECK V-LISN model NNBL 8226-2. The radiofrequency current is also measured in both lines using the probes MD 4070 (4 kHz - 400 MHz) from TESEQ and 9250-1N (10 kHz - 450 MHz) from Solar Electronics Company. The measurement parameters for R1, R2, R3, and R4 were set according to the MIL-STD-461G standard.

FIGURE 1. E2.1 - The schematic of the measurement setup. Multi-channel measurement is possible for R1 and R2. For R4, measurements are performed sequentially, one line at a time.

FIGURE 2. E2.1 - The measurement setup.

E. EMISSIONS OF A DC/DC CONVERTER USING SPREAD SPECTRUM MODULATION

The conducted emissions of a CoolGaN™ 600 V half-bridge evaluation board are measured using the setup presented in Figs. 3 and 4. This device circuit is a buck converter based on Gallium Nitrate (GaN) transistors loaded with 8.2 Ω . This GaN converter is controlled by the development board LAUNCHXL-F28379D using MATLAB Simulink. Three types of switching frequency modulation shown in Table 5. Two of them have been used to spread the spectrum of the emissions [4]. The GaN converter is supplied through the

LISN model TEKBOX TBOH01 5 μ H. The receivers used to measure the emission are R2, R8 and R9, as shown in Table 2. The RF current probe model F-33-2 (1 kHz - 250 MHz) from the positive line measures the normal mode current (I_{NM}).

TABLE 5. E2.2 - Spread spectrum modulation characteristics.

ID	PWM Type	Parameters
E2.2.1	Continuous	20 kHz, Steady
E2.2.2	Linear	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.
E2.2.3	Random	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.

FIGURE 3. E2.2 - The schematic of the measurement setup. The I_{NM} is measured via R2, R8 and R9 receivers.

FIGURE 4. E2.2 - The measurement setup.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, the results of all experiments are presented in an orderly manner from E0 to E2.2. Due to page length constraints and for clarity reasons, only the most representative results are reported in what follows. The data of test conditions that have been omitted is available upon request.

A. META-ANALYSIS OF CALIBRATION DATA

The meta-analysis of the measuring receivers' calibration data is presented below. Due to the lack of standardization in the format for presenting such calibration results, most certificates reported the results differently. Therefore, the original data was normalized and plotted as in Fig. 5 to Fig. 8 to facilitate the necessary comparisons. The "upper" and "lower" limit lines in Figs. 5 and 6 correspond to the tolerances defined in CISPR 16-1-1 for the deviation of each of the compared parameters, based on calibration data.

Fig. 5 corresponds to the sinewave voltage level error in CISPR band B when a reference CW signal is fed to the receiver. Typically, the target amplitude level is 66 dB μ V. For each receiver, the calibration points are plotted alongside error bars corresponding to the measurement uncertainty.

FIGURE 5. E0 - CISPR Band B. Sinewave level accuracy calibration results. The frequency of the calibration points might be different for each receiver unit.

Next, we present some calibration results of the response to pulses. In Fig. 6, the focus is on the QP detector error when a pulsed signal at a reference repetition rate (25 Hz) is applied. On the other hand, Fig. 7 shows the error in the PK to quasi-peak ratio (PK/QP) at the said pulse repetition frequency (PRF). The absolute and the relative response to pulses are expected to be flat in a given CISPR band for a given PRF. For the reported cases, calibration points and the measurement uncertainty are indicated in the plots.

FIGURE 6. E0 - CISPR Band A. Response to pulses. QP detector deviation at a pulse repetition frequency of 25 Hz. absolute calibration.

FIGURE 7. E0 - CISPR Band B. Response to pulses. PK/QP ratio deviation at a pulse repetition frequency of 25 Hz.

With respect to the resolution bandwidth (RBW) filter characteristics, Fig. 8 shows the 1.5 dB, 6 dB and 20 dB decay points and the RBW filter mask requirement for band A. The standard does not fix the test frequency, so this is defined by the calibration laboratory. RBW filter characteristics are very similar in all the models considered in the analysis.

FIGURE 8. E0 - CISPR Band A. Selectivity of the resolution bandwidth filter.

Data shows that direct sampling implementations do not perform differently (significantly better or worse) from receiver models using other architectures. The results for the bands or test conditions not shown above exhibit the same behaviour and lead to equivalent conclusions.

B. PULSE MODULATED SINEWAVE

Figures 9 to 11 show the error associated with the measurements obtained for each device, detector, and frequency under evaluation. It should be noted that the R2 data is not presented for the 500 MHz frequency due to the bandwidth limitations of the device.

The error limits of the graphs are between ± 1.5 dB, as this is the CISPR 16-1-1 tolerance. No significant discrepancies were observed between the R3 and R4 errors and the

FIGURE 9. E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 20 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 1 \text{ ms}$.

FIGURE 10. E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 10 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 100 \mu\text{s}$.

FIGURE 11. E1.1 - Test condition: $\tau = 50 \mu\text{s}$, $T = 1 \text{ ms}$.

oscilloscope based implementations R1 and R2. In most cases, the error remains consistently within ± 0.5 dB for all devices and detectors. The most prominent exception of this is exemplified in Fig. 11, at 100 MHz and 500 MHz, where larger deviations in the average detector were found. In all cases, test results are within CISPR tolerance.

C. ALTERNATIVE GENERATED SIGNALS

In this subsection, first the noise level measurement results of the used receivers are presented, then results E1.2.3 and E1.2.5 are selected for demonstration as representing the most remarkable cases.

1) NOISE LEVEL

Fig. 12 shows the noise floor of the receivers under test with the limit provided by MIL-STD 461G. All receivers perform noise level results at least 30 dB less than the limit line. The noise level of the R8 can be lower if the level of the used attenuator is reduced. However, this results in a lower measured voltage range. For consistency, Fig. 12 displays the noise level measurement results with uniform settings applied across all measurements.

FIGURE 12. E1.2 - Noise floor of the R2, R8 and R9 receivers.

2) SIGNALS WITH STABLE FREQUENCY CONTENT

In this subsection, the results of the three test signals with stable frequency content are reviewed together. For example, Fig. 13 presents the results of the square signal measurement via R2, R8 and R9 receivers at seven specific frequencies.

Since R8 is considered the reference device at this stage, within each pair (R2/R8 and R9/R8), the differences between their output at each specific frequency were found by (1) and (2).

$$\Delta_{R2,j} = S_{R8,j} - S_{R2,j}, \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta_{R9,j} = S_{R8,j} - S_{R9,j}, \quad (2)$$

where, $S_{R2,j}$, $S_{R8,j}$, and $S_{R9,j}$ are the amplitude values measured via R2, R8 and R9 receivers at specific frequencies j .

Then, the maximum and average differences for each test signal and detector are found by 3 and 4.

$$\Delta_{MAX,i} = \max(\Delta_{ij}), \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_{AVE,i} = \text{mean}(\Delta_{ij}), \quad (4)$$

where i corresponds to receivers under test.

Calculated Δ_{MAX} and Δ_{AVE} are listed in Table 6. As receiver R9 does not provide the average and quasi-peak detector, therefore R9 results are presented only for the peak detector. Within the E1.2.1 and E1.2.2 receivers R2 and R9 show the results with a maximum deviation of 0.43 dB from reference receiver R8 for all detectors. In E1.2.3 the

FIGURE 13. E1.2.3 - Measurement results of the square signal. Peak detector.

deviation becomes more significant, the average values in the R2/R8 pair increase up to 2 dB and the maximum deviation exceeds 3 dB for average and quasi-peak detectors. These significant deviations can be explained by the level of the measured signal at 120 kHz close to the noise level of the receivers used as can be seen in Fig. 13.

TABLE 6. E1.2 - Maximum and average differences between receivers for the alternative signals with stable frequency content.

ID	Detector	R2/R8, (dB)		R9/R8, (dB)	
		Δ_{MAX}	Δ_{AVE}	Δ_{MAX}	Δ_{AVE}
E1.2.1	PK	0.08		0.08	
	AVE	0.08		-	
	QP	0.34		-	
E1.2.2	PK	0.14	-0.09	0.18	-0.09
	AVE	0.15	-0.10	-	
	QP	0.43	-0.37	-	
E1.2.3	PK	1.67	-0.26	13.69	-4.39
	AVE	4.35	-1.00	-	
	QP	4.47	-2.02	-	

3) SIGNALS WITH TIME-VARIANT FREQUENCY CONTENT

The measurement of time-variant signals needs to be analyzed over a spectrum of frequencies rather than at distinct ones. However, the data collected from different receivers can differ in length, even though they need to be uniform for effective cross-comparison. To achieve this, the results from R8 and R9 are linearly resampled to match the length of the R2 data set, ensuring the consistency of the original output behavior. For example, in Fig. 14, the resampled results of the chirp signal (E1.2.4) are presented. Although the set amplitude of the signal is 1 V_{RMS} (120 $dB\mu V$), all receivers resulted in lower values. It is the expected measurement result of the signal with the variant frequency content over the measurement time. The probability density function (PDF) and histogram clearly visualize the difference between the measurements received. They are presented in Fig. 15.

From Fig. 14 and 15, it is clear that R2 results in more close to R8 output in comparison to R9; only several 0.5 dB deeps are noticed. For these resampled data at the frequency range under interest (from 80 kHz to 120 kHz),

FIGURE 14. E1.2.4 - Measurement results of the chirp signal.

FIGURE 15. E1.2.4 - The PDF of the chirp signal measurements.

TABLE 7. E1.2.4 - Receivers comparison for the chirp signal

Receiver Detector	R9/R8		R2/R8	
	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-0.14	0.01	0.85	0.01
\bar{d} , (dB)	-0.14	0.07	-0.08	0.26
s_d , (dB)	0.05	0.11	1.13	0.31

the differences within pairs R2/R8 and R9/R8 are found according to 1 and 2. The average difference (\bar{d}) and the standard deviation of differences (s_d) are defined, as well as the difference between the mode values (Δ_{MODE}) seen in Fig. 15.

Calculated values characterizing differences within pairs R2/R8 and R9/R8 for different detectors are presented in Table 7. Average differences over the frequency range of interest are much lower than 3 dB for all detectors. The mode value of the R8 and R2 results differs by 0.01 dB. Oppositely, R9 results in a mode value 0.14 dB dB higher. The low value of the s_d indicates that R9 results are consistently higher than R2 results throughout the frequency range.

The spectrum measurement of the E1.2.5 has four characteristic frequency spans, as shown in Fig. 16. Each frequency span is processed separately in the same way as for the chirp signal above.

The differences in peak detector measurements in R2/R8 and R9/R8 pairs are found, and for the R2/R8 pair, the results of the average and quasipeak detectors are compared and analyzed. Then, the maximum and average differences over four spans are found. Table 8 summarises the average values that characterize the differences between R2 and R9

FIGURE 16. E1.2.5 - Square signal with variant modulated frequency measurements. Peak detector.

measurements from R8. Average and maximum deviations between measurements, as well as standard deviation, show the high accuracy of using R2 receiver. The calculated deviations are in the range of ± 1 dB.

TABLE 8. E1.2.5 - Receivers comparison for the square signal with variant modulated frequency

Receiver Detector	R9/R8		R2/R8	
	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-0.19	-0.08	0.59	-0.12
\bar{d} , (dB)	-0.26	-0.05	-0.06	-0.30
s_d , (dB)	0.11	0.15	1.01	0.32

D. EMISSIONS OF A COST DC/DC CONVERTER

The results of this experiment are structured according to the most relevant observations made during the data analysis stage, including considerations about harmonic voltage level accuracy, broadband voltage level accuracy, resonances and noise floor. In particular, Fig. 17 shows the spectrum comparison between the R1, R2 and R4 for the positive line (OUT 0) of the LISN, and this case is used to exemplify the general observations.

FIGURE 17. E2.1 - Conducted emissions, positive line (LISN OUT 0).

1) HARMONIC VOLTAGE LEVEL ACCURACY

Fig. 18 to Fig. 20 show R4 delivers a coarser frequency resolution than R1 and R2 for the same basic settings. This might be explained by the type of frequency interpolation used, including the interpolation ratios and algorithms. R1 and R2 use the Akima method, while R4 applies linear interpolation.

2) BROADBAND VOLTAGE LEVEL ACCURACY

Fig. 21 shows the broadband emission spectrum measured when the resolution bandwidth is larger than the distance between individual harmonic components. An excellent agreement is observed in the spectrum amplitude for all receivers considered. To quantify the difference between R4 (reference) and the oscilloscope-based systems (R1 and R2), the deviations are calculated as,

$$\bar{\Delta}_1 = S_{R4} - S_{R1}, \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\Delta}_2 = S_{R4} - S_{R2}. \quad (6)$$

FIGURE 18. E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 189 kHz.

FIGURE 19. E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 762.5 kHz.

FIGURE 20. E2.1 - Zoom of harmonic at 1.138 MHz.

FIGURE 21. E2.1 - Broadband emissions in the range 30 MHz - 50 MHz.

Fig. 22 compares the approximated distribution of the deviations in (5) and (6) using a histogram format. The mean values of the calculated errors in that frequency range $\bar{\Delta}_1$ and $\bar{\Delta}_2$ are very close to 0 dB, being -0.16 dB and 0.06 dB, respectively.

FIGURE 22. E2.1 - Difference in the amplitude levels for broadband emissions in the range 30 MHz - 50 MHz.

3) RESONANCES

Around resonances, the spectrum amplitude changes rapidly with frequency. In this case, some examples of small resonances are found in Fig. 21. Table 9 shows the amplitude level and frequency of both resonance peaks. In those two cases, we found less than 0.5 dB and 40 kHz of difference.

TABLE 9. E2.1 - Analysis at the resonance frequencies.

	R1	R2	R4	R1	R2	R4
Level, (dBμV)	57.07	56.62	56.77	57.76	58.21	58.37
Frequency, (MHz)	30.74	30.72	30.70	43.29	43.31	43.33

4) NOISE FLOOR

Fig.23 shows the noise floor of R1, R2 and R4 compared with a conducted emissions limit; in this case, we used the limit corresponding to the CE102 test according to the MIL-STD-461G. According to the data, noise levels are sufficiently low. However, we found out that R4 in its by intended configuration (without preamplifier and with 10 dB of internal attenuation) delivered the higher noise floor.

FIGURE 23. Noise floor and standard limit comparison.

E. EMISSIONS OF A DC/DC CONVERTER USING SPREAD SPECTRUM MODULATION

The results of the EMI measurements of the DC/DC GaN converter with different PWM are presented in this subsection. In this case, the EMI is presented via normal mode current I_{NM} , and its measurements are performed via an RF current probe.

1) CONTINUOUS PULSE WIDTH MODULATION

The continuous PWM with a fundamental frequency of 20 kHz applied for the DC/DC GaN converter resulted in EMI with seven specific frequencies below 150 kHz, similar to the spectrum of the square signal, presented in Fig. 13. In Fig. 24, the measurement results of the peak detector are presented. The deviations of the R2 and R9 output from R8 measurements are defined by 1 and 2. The maximum and average deviations for the three detectors are listed in Table 10.

The receiver R2 results in a uniform deviation from the reference R8 output for all detectors in the range between 0.43 dB and 0.7 dB. Meanwhile, R9 results in a higher deviation from R2 by up to 2.96 dB at 20 kHz.

FIGURE 24. E2.2.1 - Continuous PWM. Peak detector.

TABLE 10. E2.2.1 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter controlled with continuous PWM.

Detector	R2/R8		R9/R8	
	Δ_{MAX} , (dB)	Δ_{AVE} , (dB)	Δ_{MAX} , (dB)	Δ_{AVE} , (dB)
PK	-0.43	-0.49	2.96	0.13
AV	-0.43	-0.50	-	-
QP	-0.70	-0.77	-	-

2) SPREAD SPECTRUM PULSE WIDTH MODULATION

A spread spectrum technique is used to reduce the emission detected in the standard emission tests, as it can be seen in Fig. 25, where the results of the I_{NM} measurements of the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM using the peak detector are presented. In contrast to the square signal in Fig. 16, here six specific frequency ranges can be highlighted. In Fig. 25, a high number of peaks and dips over the frequency under study are clearly seen. The I_{NM} of the DC/DC GaN converted controlled by random spread spectrum PWM is the most complex time-variant EMI within the framework of this paper. However, as can be seen in Fig. 26, the PDF for the first frequency range from 18 kHz to

FIGURE 25. E2.2.3 - The EMI from the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM.

FIGURE 26. E2.2.3 - The PDF of the EMI from the converter controlled with random spread spectrum PWM.

22 kHz shows very similar results for peak detectors of the receivers under study.

For both results of the E2.2.2 and E2.2.3 the analyses similar to the one used for the generated signals with time-variant frequency content are performed and listed in Table 11 and 12, respectively. The E2.2.2 results in the average deviation from the R2 output is less than 2 dB, for all detectors. The standard deviations are up to 1.17 dB. Meanwhile, for the emission from the DC/DC converter with random spread spectrum PWM, despite the measured signal's complexity, the R2 results' average deviation for all detectors is within 3 dB. It's also quite remarkable that the differences between R9 and R8 are slightly larger than in pair R2/R8.

TABLE 11. E2.2.2 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter with linear spread spectrum PWM. Average deviations from R8.

Receiver	R9/R8		R2/R8	
	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-0.99	-1.24	-1.30	-2.22
d_s , (dB)	-1.21	-1.09	-1.09	-1.63
s_d , (dB)	0.45	0.43	1.17	0.55

TABLE 12. E2.2.3 - Receivers comparison for the EMI from the converter with random spread spectrum PWM. Average deviations from R8.

Receiver	R9/R8		R2/R8	
	PK	PK	AVE	QP
Δ_{MODE} , (dB)	-2.49	-1.42	1.04	-2.45
d_s , (dB)	-2.63	-1.40	0.54	-2.44
s_d , (dB)	2.53	2.72	2.80	1.53

V. CONCLUSION

Previous works have verified the performance of time-domain measuring receivers based on direct sampling instruments. However, the corresponding evidence remained scattered and focused either on calibration data or specific use cases. This study bridged that gap by providing a sequence of validations through a multi-level approach. In five different experiments, commercial EMI receivers (frequency-swept and FFT-based) were compared with an oscilloscope-based counterpart (R1 and R2) following an approach where the complexity of the excitation signals increased progressively.

Based on the results obtained, it is concluded that R1 and R2 performed as well as their CISPR 16-1-1 compliant counterparts in the frequency and amplitude ranges evaluated; that is, the measurement errors in various test conditions remained well within standard tolerances. It is essential to recall that this is the first work where such multi-level and extensive empirical validation has been explicitly carried out, in collaboration with independent teams, to benchmark direct sampling implementations of FFT-based measuring receivers with commercial solutions.

The robustness of the work is grounded in the combined representativeness of the different scenarios and the size of the test sample used. Because of page length restrictions and for the sake of conciseness, this article presents only a subset of representative results to support our claims. In all cases, the authors commit to sharing the complete measurement data upon request for those interested.

We expect this work will contribute to leveraging EMC standardization by supporting the explicit mention of EMI receivers based on direct sampling instruments. Widening the measuring receiver definition in this way would open up a broad range of possibilities for new measurement setups based on multi-channel and full time-domain capabilities. Such features, previously exploited in research projects, bring advantages that are called for widespread applications in the practice of EMC.

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IVAN STRUZHKO (Student Member, IEEE) holds a BSc degree in electrical engineering (2013) and an MSc degree in electrical power engineering, electrical engineering, and electromechanics (2015), both from Pryazovskyi State Technical University, Ukraine. Since then, he has worked as an electric and power energy engineer at the Armavirskiy Machine Building Plant and as a teaching assistant at the Department of Electrical Engineering of the Pryazovskyi State Technical University. Since October 2021, he has

been working towards the PhD degree in electromagnetic compatibility with the Power Electronics and Electromagnetic Compatibility Group at the University of Twente. His research interest is focused on the implementation of the cognitive radio concept for the EMC applications.

MARC GARCÍA-BERMÚDEZ holds a BSc degree in electronic engineering and telecommunications from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) and is currently enrolled in the Master's degree program in Aerospace Science and Technology at the same university. Currently, he is a research intern at EMC Barcelona, actively supporting the 21NRM06 project "Metrology for Emerging Electromagnetic Compatibility Standards" and the company activities as incubatees of the ESA Business

Incubation Center in Barcelona.

JORDI SOLÉ-LLOVERAS (Member, IEEE) holds a BSc degree in telecommunication engineering (2020) and an MSc degree in electronics engineering (2022), both from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). He is pursuing a PhD with research focused on in situ emissions assessments of large systems. Since 2018, he has been part of the Grup de Compatibilitat Electromagnètica of UPC, where he has been involved in testing and technology transfer projects. Since 2021, he has worked at

EMC Barcelona, where he participates in R&D and consultancy projects.

MANUEL AÑÓN-CANCELA received the MSc degree in physics from Universidade de Santiago de Compostela in 1989. He joined INTA in 1991 as an E3 test engineer in the Electromagnetic Compatibility Area, being involved in several national and international projects for the aerospace and defense sectors. He is currently the Head of the EMC area at INTA. He is a member of national and international standardization groups for military and civilian E3 specs.

TOM HARTMAN (S'20-M'22) received His BSc in electrical engineering, in 2016, MSc in electrical engineering in 2018, and his PhD (Cum Laude) in EMC in 2023 at the University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands, where he is currently working as an assistant professor. He had the honour of receiving the 2021 President Memorial Award of the IEEE EMC Society and the 2022 Richard B. Shultz Best Transaction Paper Award of IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility for the journal paper entitled:

"Susceptibility of Static Energy Meters Due to Amplifier Clipping Caused by a Rogowski Coil".

MARCO A. AZPÚRUA (Senior Member, IEEE) received a BSc degree in telecommunications (2008) and an MSc in electrical engineering (2013) from the Universidad Central de Venezuela. In 2018, received a PhD degree in Electronics Engineering from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Spain. Currently, he works as an Assoc. Prof. of the Electronic Engineering Department at UPC, where he is part of the EMC Group. Dr. Azpúrua is the Co-founder of EMC Barcelona, a fellow of the StandICT.eu projects

(2023 and 2026) and a member of the CISPR/CIS/B/WG 1 & WG 7, the IEEE EMC and IMS societies, and the IEEE/ICES.

Frank Leferink (Fellow, IEEE) received the BSc, MSc, and PhD degrees in electrical engineering from the University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands, in 1984, 1992, and 2001, respectively. Since 1984, he has been with THALES in Hengelo, The Netherlands, and is currently the Director EMC. He is also Manager of the Network of Excellence on EMC, THALES Group, with more than 100 EMC engineers scattered over more than 20 units, worldwide. In 2003 he joined as

(part-time, full research) Professor and holds the the Chair for EMC with the University of Twente. He has authored and coauthored more than 300 papers published at international conferences or peer reviewed journals, and he holds five patents. Prof. dr. Leferink is the past President of the Dutch EMC-ESD association, Chair of the IEEE EMC Benelux Chapter, member of ISC EMC Europe, the Chairman of EMC Europe 2018 (Amsterdam, The Netherlands), a Member of the Board of Directors of the IEEE EMC Society, and Associate Editor of the IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility and the IEEE Letters on Electromagnetic Compatibility Practice and Applications.